

CONSIDERATIONS ON THE SOCIAL-HISTORICAL ROOTS OF FAMILY AND MARRIAGE CEREMONIES

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Abstract. *The article discusses the modernization of ancient religious beliefs, traditions related to Zoroastrianism, and Islamic traditions in the wedding customs, traditions and ceremonies of the Uzbek people.*

Keywords: *Avesta, Zoroastrianism, customs and traditions, wedding, suitor, groom, bridegroom greetings, open face, chilla.*

It is known that one of the most attractive ceremonies of the Uzbek people, which embodies the ancient customs, worldview, beliefs, lifestyle, life experiences and skills accumulated over the centuries, is the wedding. In studying the ancient beliefs, cultural history, dreams and hopes of our people, the rituals related to the wedding are important. Wedding days have long been considered one of the best days for Uzbeks. That's why old people always pray: "Let everyone get to the wedding, let them see their dreams." One of the main and structural issues of a wedding is, of course, family and marital relations.

The word family has five different dictionary meanings in the Uzbek language. Family - a set of people living together, consisting of a couple, their children and their closest relatives; the apartment. Its other meanings are close to each other, and in a general sense, one can say groups of people, people, countries, or groups of plants and animals, a group of sister languages. In addition, in the dictionary, family also means wife in the colloquial language. The "Islam" encyclopedia does not provide information about the concept of family, unlike marriage. In general, the family is a small group based on marriage or birth, which has been held as a special ceremony in our people since ancient times. That is, in order to celebrate the fact that the two young people got married and started a family, a dinner was held, and the community of relatives and neighbors gathered.

If we focus on the ancient roots of the marriage ceremony, we will be able to see that it has gained importance in all eras. Zoroastrianism, which was practiced by our ancestors who lived in Central Asia, had marriage ceremonies typical of its time. According to the rules of Zoroastrianism, all people must live as a couple, that is, get married on the basis of a family. "That's why in Avesta great importance is attached to the issue of family and family upbringing, and the human duty is not only to learn moral guidelines, but also the need for a person's family life to be happy and cheerful, to think about a good husband and a good child... It is said that the important thing is that in order for a man to get married and have offspring, it must first be materially and spiritually full, physically strong, spiritually and physically flawless..

Accordingly, in Zoroastrianism, in order to regulate family relations, issues such as the fact that every man should be healthy, have the ability and strength to make a living, and raise the child to be born in the family in a perfect manner are of particular importance. To start a family, the presence of factors that serve to make the boy and girl happy and happy is aimed at fulfilling the commitment and family duty.

According to the Avesta, teenagers are considered adults and have the right to marry when they turn 15. But young people are not allowed to start a family arbitrarily. Building a family was the responsibility of the community and parents. For this reason, the team and parents have carefully considered the future bride and groom. A healthy girl of tall stature and color was selected for a young man who was perfect in every way, and her pedigree was investigated.

So, we can see that our ancestors followed the proverb "Measure seven, cut one" in matters of marriage. Therefore, the ideas related to building a family in "Avesta" have been passed down from ancestors to generations in the process of historical development on the basis of religious beliefs. According to the historical facts that have come down to us, "...if a man had the ability to leave offspring, but did not marry, he was branded or forced to wear a heavy iron belt around his waist all the time. "The unmarried girl was put in a bag and beaten with 25 lashes." Such punishments show that the Zoroastrians intend to continue the next generation, especially that each person must obey strict laws to become his successors.

Marriage relations in the teachings of Zoroastrianism and a number of marriage-related issues of our citizens with a modern worldview, including the issue of not allowing relatives to start a family, are explained. It embodies a unique philosophical wisdom. Firstly, according to the results of today's medicine, it has been scientifically proven that the family of close relatives leads to unhealthy births, various mental illnesses, birth defects. Secondly, the presence of close relatives in marriage does not correspond to our spirituality in some aspects. Social life itself proves that if young people in such a married family do not get along with each other and a situation occurs that eventually leads to their separation, lifelong enmity of relatives will also arise.

Such aspects are even described in the "Vandidod" chapter of the Avesta, special attention is paid to the hereditary aspects of the health of the offspring, and the marriage of children between close relatives is prohibited by law. In order to prevent the birth of a defective child, practical considerations were made and parents were given useful advice. From this we can see that such a marriage reflects the seriousness and reasonableness of our ancestors' relationship to the future.

Zoroastrians prepared their children for family from a young age. Every young man and woman should learn the customs and traditions of their family and people carefully and be ready for the process of starting a family. "After that, girls at the age of 15 and boys at the age of 16 were given a special test in front of the team under the leadership of an elder. As a result, girls who have reached the age of majority have learned to earn a living and become "katbonu", i.e. "housewives", while young men have the right to be "kadhudo" i.e. "head of the family", take shepherd's fields, ride horses, ride camels... "The men got married from the age of 16." This is the test that shows whether Zoroastrians are ready for a family or have defects.

In "Avesta" expressing opinions about the relevance of human life as a family, it is noted that this process is mainly determined by moral purity, glorification of human feelings, and the conscious activity of a person unlike other creatures. It is emphasized that the highest emotions in humans arise on the basis of marriage, and in other creatures it is the continuation of heredity or animal greed. In this regard, Friedrich Niche expressed his views: "You have a lot of short-lived insanities - this is what you call love." Your marriage will end so many short insanities as one long insanity.

Your love for your wife and your wife's love for the earth - oh, if only it were compassion for the suffering and the hidden gods! But two creatures always find each other.

Even your best love is only a symbol of exaltation and pain is lust. Love is a torch that illuminates the highest paths.

Thirst in the creator, longing for a great person and arrows - my brother, tell me, is this what you want for marriage?

For me, such a marriage and such a will are sacred.

The sacred bond called marriage was formed in Zoroastrianism as a system of moral norms that regulates human actions and character in everyday life. In it, special attention is paid to the rights of the family, the manifestations of the crime related to it, and the responsibility for the prohibited actions in the family. These, in turn, represent the preservation of the strict ancestral religious beliefs of each marriage, secondly, they directly served to strengthen the family, and thirdly, they served to prevent divorces.

In Zoroastrianism, "Crimes against religion - relations with representatives of different religions, starting a family, duties and responsibilities of priests, impiety, etc., crimes against morality - adultery between spouses, and other serious moral crimes" were punished based on strict laws.

Their relationship to the family is strong, and it is important to always respect and honor the rights of women in the family, to ensure its integrity and continuation in the future, and to make each family member aware of their duties. In particular, the father must fulfill his duty in the family, i.e. his obligation to support his wife and children, and the educational role of the mother in the development of children, i.e. preparing girls for marriage from a young age, teaching them virtue and purity, and children's unconditional fulfillment of their duties to their parents. thrown in the middle.

Like other religions, Zoroastrianism only allowed one marriage per man. The community did not allow the family to break up due to the inability of the husband and wife to get along with each other, the mother-in-law's or mother-in-law's displeasure, conspiracy, slander, and backbiting. Marriage is annulled only in case of sexual or mental defect of one of the parties or in case of adultery. Fornication and fornication are strongly condemned. Adulterers could atone for their sins by building a bridge over 14 ditches.

In "Avesta", a number of legal norms related to the annulment of marriage are determined based on the rules of the society. According to it, a number of rules for annulment of marriage are indicated on the basis of the fact that the spouses have equal rights. In particular, if after the marriage one of the young men or women shows physical or mental weakness or the physically healthy party has the right to annul this marriage. Or if the man lacked manhood, in which case the woman had the right to divorce her husband.

Another rule was established that if a man could not financially support the family for three years, such a man was abandoned by the woman, i.e. divorced. If a husband or wife commits adultery in a family, this marriage is considered "haram" and each party divorces the other party.

One of the important rules of this period was related to religious affiliation. Talaq is obligatory if a man or a woman turns away from the religion practiced in the society, that is, from the Zoroastrian religion, that is, if he accepts another religion. Because the family is considered sacred in Zoroastrianism, it is not allowed to annul the marriage for other reasons, including incitement, slander, disagreement between the spouses, and the excuse of not being able to meet the parents. The sin of slander, backbiting, and hatred among women is severely condemned. Provocateurs who spoke were punished by flogging".

Such religious rules served to ensure that Zoroastrians strictly adhere to their beliefs in the society, as well as to ensure the stability of each family and the harmony and harmony of citizens. Therefore, in "Avesta" it is written that "a person who has served the path of beauty and goodness,

light and happiness throughout his life is righteous, pure and fair, and welcomes guests with generosity and open-mindedness. It is said that because he loves his neighbor, takes care of the land and livestock, does not pay attention to people's wealth, preserves nature and enjoys it, his soul is filled with inexhaustible pleasure and relaxation.”

In "Avesta", the marriage ceremonies that have been practiced by our people since time immemorial have preserved their continuity and relevance despite the passage of centuries. The moral and aesthetic manifestations of national ceremonies in them show that humanity has been united on the basis of the sacred concept of the so-called family since ancient times. Therefore, our ancestors developed their spiritual world in harmony with high moral principles and left a unique aesthetic outlook to future generations.

In general, the traditional wedding ceremonies of Uzbeks are made up of a set of ancient customs and ceremonies, most of which have been combined with Islamic traditions and continue to this day. It is the main reason for the viability of these rituals and customs, their main content and highest goal is to ensure continuity of future generations.

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